

Additional online materials - Persistent changes in motor adaptation strategies after perturbations that require exploration of novel muscle activation patterns

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Methods

EMG-to-force mapping

For controlling the cursor in the EMG control mode, we created a mapping between recorded muscle activities and the movement of the cursor displayed in the virtual scene. The force generated at the hand was approximated as a linear function of the recorded arm and shoulder muscle activations: $\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{H} \mathbf{m}$, where \mathbf{f} is the force vector acting on the virtual cursor, \mathbf{m} is the 16-dimensional vector of muscle activations, and \mathbf{H} is a matrix relating muscle activation to force. Such EMG-to-force matrix (\mathbf{H}) was estimated using multiple linear regressions of each applied force component, low-pass filtered (second-order Butterworth; 1 Hz cutoff), with the EMG signals recorded during the initial force control block (Block 2, during the static phase, defined as the time interval in which the cursor was within the target), low-pass filtered (second-order Butterworth; 5 Hz cutoff) and normalized to the maximum EMG activity during the generation of MVF. Only muscles that significantly contributed to the EMG-to-force mapping, were included in the calculation of the EMG-to-force mapping. This was estimated by the confidence interval (95%) for the coefficient estimates of the multiple linear regression.

Muscle synergy extraction

Muscle synergies were identified by NMF (1) from EMG patterns recorded during the initial force control block (Block 2, during the static phase): $\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{W} \mathbf{c}$, with \mathbf{W} the $M \times N$ synergy matrix, \mathbf{c} the N -dimensional synergy activation vector, where N is the number of synergies, and M the number of

muscles. EMG patterns were first low-pass filtered (second-order Butterworth filter; 5 Hz cut-off frequency) and rectified, their baseline noise level was then subtracted, and finally normalized to the maximum EMG activity of each muscle recorded during the generation of MVF. The number of synergies (N) was then selected according to two criteria: (1) the N at which there was a change in the slope of the R^2 curve as a function of N and (2) the smallest N explaining at least 90% of the variation of the data. In case of a mismatch between the two criteria, we selected the synergies set whose preferred directions had the smallest number of preferred directions with small angular differences and were distributed more uniformly. The preferred directions were evaluated by the direction of the maximum of the cosine function best fitting the directional tuning of the synergy activation coefficients. A detailed description of the selection of the number of synergies can be found in our previous report (2).

Construction of virtual surgeries

For each participant, a compatible and an incompatible virtual surgery were created by modifying the EMG-to-force mapping according to the muscle synergies identified in the force control block at the beginning of the experimental session (Block 2, see below). After the compatible virtual surgery, the forces associated with the muscle synergies still spanned the whole force space. In contrast, after the incompatible virtual surgery, the forces associated with the muscle synergies did not span the entire force space. Consequently, the perturbation could not be compensated for by recombining the muscle synergies, and novel muscle activations were required. A detailed description of the construction of an incompatible virtual surgery can be found in our previous report (3).

Experimental task and protocol

Each participant performed a single experimental session (see Figure 1 for an illustration of the experimental protocol). At the beginning of the experimental session, participants performed two blocks of trials in force control. In the first force control block (B1), the mean maximum voluntary force (MVF) along eight directions (separated by 45°) in the horizontal plane was estimated as the mean of the maximum force magnitude recorded across 16 trials in which participants were instructed to generate maximum force in each direction. Participants were then instructed to perform a center-out reaching task with a cursor on a horizontal plane by applying isometric force on a simulated mass-spring-damper system. They had to maintain the cursor in a central start

location for 1 s (tolerance of 2% MVF), reach a target as soon as it appeared, as quickly as possible, at one of eight peripheral locations, and maintain the cursor at the target for 1 s (tolerance of 2% MVF). A successful trial had to be completed within 15 seconds from its onset. The second force control block consisted of 72 trials of reaching targets in 8 directions at 3 force magnitudes (10%, 20%, and 30% MVF). After this block, there was a 5-minute break to process the recorded data and to compute the EMG-to-force matrix and the muscle synergies necessary to construct a participant-specific myoelectric controller and participant-specific virtual surgeries. After the initial two blocks in force control, for the rest of the experimental session participants performed the task in EMG control. Each EMG control block consisted of 24 trials with the 8 targets at 20% MVF in random order, with exception of the blocks without visual feedback of the cursor position, which consisted of 8 trials each. In the first EMG control block (FAM), participants were familiarized with the new control modality. Then participants performed two series of blocks of compatible and incompatible virtual surgeries, respectively (see *Section* above: “*Construction of virtual surgeries*”). Each series consisted of 15 blocks: two baseline blocks, one HIDDEN block, eight virtual surgery blocks, one HIDDEN block, two washout blocks, and one HIDDEN block. Half of the subjects were first introduced to the series of compatible virtual surgery; the other half were first introduced to the series of incompatible virtual surgery. In between the two series, participants rested for 10 min; they were also allowed to rest at any time during the experiment.

Figure 1. Experimental Protocol. Each participant participated in a single experimental session that included 16 trials of maximum voluntary force generation in eight directions (B1, MVF), and 72 reaching trials to targets located in eight directions at three force magnitudes (10%, 20%, and 30% MVF) in force control (B2,

BL). The following blocks of 24 trials each (with exception of the HIDDEN blocks which consisted of eight trials each) in EMG control: one block of familiarization (B3, FAM) and two series of 15 blocks for each surgery type: two baseline blocks (B4-5, EMG BL), one HIDDEN block (B6), eight surgery blocks (B7-B14), one HIDDEN block (B15), two washout blocks (B16-B17), one HIDDEN block (B18). Either the compatible virtual surgery was performed first, followed by the incompatible virtual surgery (top, A), or the incompatible virtual surgery was carried out first, followed by the compatible virtual surgery (bottom, B).

References

1. **Lee DD, Seung HS.** Learning the parts of objects by non-negative matrix factorization. *Nature* 401: 788–791, 1999. doi: 10.1038/44565.
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